

Constraint-Aware AoV Planning for Orchestrating Autonomous Geospatial Analysis with LLMs

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Abstract

This paper presents a spatially aware Activity-on-Vertex (AoV) planning approach for automated geospatial workflow generation using large language models (LLMs). We propose an approach comprising context enrichment, LLM planning, and spatial validation: user queries are enriched with spatial metadata, JSON-serialized AoV workflows are generated via LLM planning, and every dependency edge is validated for coordinate reference system compatibility, geometry-type consistency, and extent overlap before execution. Evaluation of 50 GeoAnalystBench tasks with three open-weight models (Qwen3-8B, Phi-4-14B, and Gemma3-27B) shows that all three models converge at 78% semantic similarity regardless of parameter count. Results confirm that spatial constraint injection with rule-based post-validation enables locally deployable models to produce geometrically valid geospatial workflows without proprietary LLM dependencies.

Keywords: geosAI, LLM planning, workflow automation, spatial constraints, Activity-on-Vertex

1. Introduction

Automating geospatial analysis through natural language allows domain experts without programming skills to access advanced geoprocessing tools. Although large language models (LLMs) have shown strong performance in task planning (Niu, Song, Lian, et al. 2025; Bhattaram, Chung, Chung, et al. 2025; Li, Xu, Mei, et al. 2024), geospatial workflows present unique challenges. Each operation must follow the rules of the coordinate reference system (CRS), maintain valid geometry, and handle diverse data types (Zhang et al. 2024). General-purpose LLMs and multi-agent frameworks built on top of them lack this spatial knowledge and may generate workflows that are geometrically incorrect.

Here, we present a spatially aware planning approach that builds geospatial knowledge directly into an LLM-driven workflow generation process, producing executable Activity-on-Vertex (AoV) plans with verified spatial constraints. Existing multi-agent frameworks such as MetaGPT (Hong, Zhuge, Chen, et al. 2023), CAMEL (Li, Hammoud, Itani, et al. 2023), and AutoGen (Wu, Bansal, Zhang, et al. 2023) generate tasks in sequence, which is inefficient for complex geospatial queries.

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Flow (Niu, Song, Lian, et al. 2025) supports parallel task structures through AoV graphs but does not handle spatial reasoning, and GeoFlow (Bhattaram, Chung, Chung, et al. 2025) targets API-level optimization rather than workflow planning. Geo-specific systems such as GeoGPT (Zhang et al. 2024) and AutonomousGIS (Li and Ning 2023) connect GIS tools to LLM reasoning but catch spatial errors at runtime rather than checking them before execution. These gaps motivate the need for a planner that supports both parallel execution and spatial correctness.

2. Methodology

The proposed methodology is built around a spatially aware AoV graph, a type of directed acyclic graph in which vertices represent tasks and edges denote precedence relations (Niu, Song, Lian, et al. 2025). In our system, each vertex encodes a geospatial operation together with its spatial constraints, and each directed edge enforces the execution order between dependent operations. A specialized LLM-driven planner agent translates natural language geospatial queries into executable AoV plans, as illustrated in Figure 1.

Figure 1: The proposed system comprises **Context Enrichment** (2.1), where the user query is augmented with spatial metadata and domain knowledge; **LLM Planning** (2.3), where the agent generates a JSON-serialized AoV under a constrained output schema; and **Spatial Validation** (2.4), which enforces CRS compatibility, geometry-type consistency, and extent overlap on every dependency edge.

2.1. Context Enrichment

Before planning begins, the raw user query q is combined with two structured knowledge sources to form the enriched context

$$\mathcal{E} = (q, \mathcal{C}, \mathcal{K})$$

where \mathcal{C} the data catalog is annotated with spatial metadata (bounding boxes, native CRS, geometry types) and \mathcal{K} the domain knowledge base injected as a structured system prompt. \mathcal{K} covers three rule categories: (i) *CRS rules* geographic coordinates (EPSG:4326) for global data, projected UTM zones for metric operations, and automatic reprojection when CRS values differ across consecutive tasks; (ii) *vector operation constraints* geometry-type requirements per operation (e.g., area calculations require `Polygon`, spatial joins require matching dimensionality), and overlay rules enforcing CRS alignment before set operations; and (iii) *raster operation constraints* resolution and CRS consistency for multi-layer raster analysis, and index formulas for remote-sensing operations (e.g., NDVI). The tools registry \mathcal{T} is passed separately and, together with \mathcal{E} , forms provides the full planning context for LLM-driven planning.

2.2. Workflow Representation

We utilize an LLM to dynamically generate workflows, which are serialized as JSON-formatted AoV graphs. We formalize workflows as $\mathcal{G} = (V, E, \Phi_V, \Phi_E, \alpha)$, where V represents task vertices, E denotes precedence edges, Φ_V maps vertices to spatial constraints, Φ_E captures data flow, and $\alpha : V \rightarrow \mathcal{A}$ assigns vertices to worker agents. Each vertex $v_i = \langle id_i, type_i, \alpha_i, \mathcal{I}_i, \mathcal{O}_i, \Theta_i, \mathcal{S}_i \rangle$ encodes operation type, input/output specifications, parameters, and spatial constraints $\mathcal{S}_i = \langle CRS_{req}, \mathcal{G}_{valid}, \mathcal{B}_{extent} \rangle$.

2.3. LLM-Driven Planning

The Planner Agent receives the enriched context \mathcal{E} together with the tools registry \mathcal{T} and transforms queries into workflows through $\mathcal{P} : Q \times \mathcal{C} \times \mathcal{T} \times \mathcal{K} \times \mathcal{A} \rightarrow \mathcal{G}$, where \mathcal{A} is the set of specialized worker agents and \mathcal{G} is the resulting executable AoV workflow. The LLM receives spatially enriched prompts that embed geospatial reasoning rules, enabling it to decompose complex queries into atomic operations while respecting spatial constraints. CRS assignment first consults a place-name lookup table; if no match is found, the system queries Nominatim⁰ for the appropriate UTM zone, caching results and defaulting to EPSG:4326 on failure. Constraints are attached post-parsing so the LLM focuses on operation selection, and consecutive tasks with differing CRSs trigger automatic reprojection. We evaluate the proposed method using three open-weight models running locally via Ollama: Qwen3-8B (Alibaba, 8B), Phi-4-14B (Microsoft, 14B), and Gemma3-27B (Google, 27B). These models span three parameter scales and three independent families, enabling analysis of capacity effects on spatial workflow quality while ensuring full reproducibility without commercial API dependencies.

2.4. Spatial Validation

Once the LLM generates a workflow, each task carries CRS, geometry type, and bounding box fields as structured JSON. Validation is then entirely rule-based: the system applies three deterministic checks: CRS compatibility (\mathcal{V}_{CRS}), geometry type compatibility (\mathcal{V}_{geom}), and spatial extent overlap (\mathcal{V}_{extent}). The CRS compatibility check \mathcal{V}_{CRS} inserts an explicit reprojection task when the source and target CRS differ. If reprojection is not feasible, the workflow is rejected. The geometry-type check \mathcal{V}_{geom} verifies that each operation receives a compatible geometry (e.g., area

0. <https://nominatim.org>

calculations require `Polygon`, spatial joins require matching dimensionality). The extent check $\mathcal{V}_{\text{extent}}$ verifies that paired datasets share a common spatial footprint:

$$(X_{min}^{(1)} \leq X_{max}^{(2)}) \wedge (X_{min}^{(2)} \leq X_{max}^{(1)}) \wedge (Y_{min}^{(1)} \leq Y_{max}^{(2)}) \wedge (Y_{min}^{(2)} \leq Y_{max}^{(1)})$$

A workflow proceeds to execution only when every edge satisfies all three checks, i.e.

$$Valid(\mathcal{G}) = \bigwedge_{e_{i,j} \in E} [\mathcal{V}_{\text{CRS}}(v_i, v_j) \wedge \mathcal{V}_{\text{geom}}(v_i, v_j) \wedge \mathcal{V}_{\text{extent}}(v_i, v_j)]$$

These checks form the foundational validation layer, with higher-order spatial rules deferred to future work.

2.5. Evaluation Protocol

We use GPT-4o-mini (Gu, Jiang, Shi, et al. 2024) as an automated judge to score generated workflows against GeoAnalystBench (Zhang, Gao, Wei, et al. 2025) on a 0–100 scale across five criteria: Overall Similarity, Functional Accuracy, Logical Ordering, Procedural Completeness, and Effectiveness. The score range for each metric M across evaluated tasks T is defined as

$$\text{Range}(M) = [\min_{i \in T} M_i, \max_{i \in T} M_i] \quad (1)$$

GeoAnalystBench provides 50 expert-validated geospatial tasks, each paired with a reference workflow. Automated scoring targets semantic and procedural equivalence rather than exact syntactic matching, since the same process can be expressed at varying levels of abstraction.

3. Results

Figure 2: Interface (left) and parallel AoV of a generated workflow (right), showing concurrent branches for local-CRS buffering and global-CRS attribution converging before final export.

Table 1: LLM-judged similarity scores per model and aggregated mean across all three models (150 evaluated workflows, 50 tasks each). All scores on a 0–100 scale.

Metric	Qwen3-8B (8B)	Phi-4-14B (14B)	Gemma3-27B (27B)	Mean	Range
Overall Similarity	78.5	78.0	77.5	78	20–95
Accuracy	86.7	86.5	85.3	86	20–95
Ordering	88.2	84.3	85.3	86	0–95
Completion	89.3	87.7	85.0	87	0–100
Effectiveness	87.1	83.5	80.8	84	10–95

The spatially aware planner achieves a mean overall similarity score of 78% across 150 evaluated workflows (all three models combined, 50 tasks each), indicating consistent alignment with expert workflows. Procedural Completeness (87%) and Functional Accuracy (86%) are the strongest dimensions, demonstrating effective task decomposition and correct identification of required geospatial operations. Logical Ordering (86%) and Effectiveness (84%) further indicate that the generated workflows respect dependency constraints while enabling efficient execution, as illustrated by the parallel AoV structure in Figure 2.

Table 1 summarizes the evaluation results. The most notable finding is that overall semantic similarity converges narrowly at 78% across all three models, indicating that workflow quality is consistent regardless of model size. Qwen3-8B (8B parameters) achieves the highest similarity (78.5%) alongside the strongest ordering (88) and completion (89) scores, while Gemma3-27B scores lowest on effectiveness (81), suggesting that larger models do not inherently produce more executable workflows under this evaluation protocol. Performance is weakest on *making predictions* and *finding best locations and paths* tasks, which require iterative or optimization-oriented reasoning beyond single-pass workflow generation.

4. Discussion

The most notable finding is that overall similarity converges narrowly at 78% across all three models regardless of parameter count: Qwen3-8B (8B, 78.5%) matches Gemma3-27B (27B, 77.5%), while attaining the highest Ordering (88) and Completion (89) scores. We hypothesize that the structured output schema and spatially enriched prompts reduce variance across model scales, though an ablation study would be needed to confirm the relative contribution of each component. Performance is weakest on *finding the best locations and paths* tasks, which require iterative multi-criteria reasoning beyond single-pass generation. This study has four limitations.

First, the single automated judge (GPT-4o-mini) may score workflows based on surface similarity to training patterns rather than correctness, since two valid workflows that order operations differently could receive different scores. Second, we did not ablate the pipeline without the spatial validator, so the individual contribution of each check (\mathcal{V}_{CRS} , $\mathcal{V}_{\text{geom}}$, $\mathcal{V}_{\text{extent}}$) remains unquantified. Third, workflow quality is assessed by comparison to a reference on paper rather than by execution. Fourth, GeoAnalystBench derives from ScienceAgentBench (Chen, Chen, Ning, et al. 2024). LLMs trained on web corpora may have encountered these tasks, making reported scores potentially optimistic.

5. Conclusion and Future Work

This work demonstrates that integrating explicit spatial validation into Activity-on-Vertex (AoV) planning enables LLM-driven systems to generate executable geospatial workflows that respect core geographic constraints. Evaluation against GeoAnalystBench shows strong semantic alignment with expert-designed workflows, particularly in task completeness and functional accuracy, while preserving correct dependency ordering and execution efficiency. Future work will add a second judge for inter-rater agreement, run ablation experiments to quantify each constraint check, and adopt execution-based metrics once the pipeline matures.

The validator will be extended to cover topological rules (e.g., adjacency and containment between geometries) and time-aware constraints for workflows that combine raster layers from multiple dates. A follow-up publication will detail the full multi-agent architecture and evaluate the framework on additional benchmarks.

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